

1 **Bmp2 participates in germ layer lineage choice of pluripotent stem cells.**

2 Shahan K. Mamoor, B.S., M.S., Ph.D cand.¹
3 ¹shahanmamoor@gmail.com
4 Chestnut Hill, MA USA 02467
5 East Islip, NY USA 11730

6 The organ systems of the human body are each derived from three germ layers: the endoderm,
7 mesoderm, and ectoderm. We defined here using transcriptomics a minimal set of components required or
8 important for germ layer fate choice to the endoderm in the first trimester of human development. We
9 describe a requirement for Bmp2 in germ layer lineage choice from pluripotent stem cells in *Homo*
10 *sapiens*.

11 Citations

12 1. Tsuji, K., Bandyopadhyay, A., Harfe, B.D., Cox, K., Kakar, S., Gerstenfeld, L., Einhorn, T., Tabin,
13 C.J. and Rosen, V., 2006. BMP2 activity, although dispensable for bone formation, is required for the
14 initiation of fracture healing. *Nature genetics*, 38(12), pp.1424-1429.